

The USSR: an empire born, an empire dead – consequences. The Russian-Ukrainian war and the intervention of the European Union and NATO – A multipolar world in the making.

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Abstract : This article concerns the emergence of the USSR and its collapse. Was the collapse of the USSR a godsend for Western countries and NATO? The article also addresses the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war and offers reflections on the European Union, Russia, and the United States in a context of war and competing interests.

A multipolar world is taking shape, with countries unwilling to lose their sovereignty and increasingly opposed to a globalist, "monopolar" ideology. Are other countries attracted to this multipolar world in the making? Could it be to free themselves from neocolonialism? Do the BRICS countries offer a model based on global trade, unencumbered by ideology?

The Global South accuses Western countries of being neocolonialists, preventing African countries from being fully sovereign politically, economically, and ideologically. They accuse the West of provoking coups to put puppets loyal to neocolonial countries in power. Is it true that Westerners are the first to accuse others of interfering in the affairs of a state when they themselves do the same?

Are hypocrisy and double standards undermining trust in the West?

I. The USSR, an empire born in opposition to Western Europe

In early 1917, revolution was brewing in Russia and Tsar Nicholas II was overthrown. A few months later, in October 1917, Lenin took power with the Bolsheviks. He established a Soviet Russia, composed of workers, peasants, and soldiers. But a civil war broke out between the "White Army," supported by the Western powers, and the "Red Army," supported by Lenin's Bolsheviks. An ideology was born and spread throughout the empire: Marxism-Leninism.

On December 30, 1922, the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) was born with the ratification of a treaty. This treaty united the Russian SFSR, Belarus, Ukraine, and the Transcaucasian Federation. Georgia, Armenia, and Azerbaijan emerged from this federation.

Following the First Congress of Soviets, the Constitution was adopted in 1924. The Soviets had several objectives:

- To unify the republics that were previously under the rule of the Tsar of Russia.
- To confront the bloc of countries considered capitalists, and therefore hostile to their political ideology.
- To centralize power, while respecting the autonomy of the various republics. History would show us that the central government did not respect this "autonomy," as it became increasingly oppressive.

- To establish a Communist Party that did not tolerate opposition.
- Create a centralized federal state, but in theory with a right of secession. This right would be used for the first time in 1991, following the collapse of the USSR.
- Centralize power over the army, foreign trade, the postal service, and telecommunications, i.e., the essentials.

II. Reflections on the centralization of power, cultures, attempts at assimilation, globalist ideology, the European Union, and its designs

Centralization of power always leads to a reduction in the prerogatives and autonomy of the regions. Excessive centralization can lead to dictatorship. The more culturally and linguistically homogeneous an empire is, the longer it can hope to last. However, it is difficult to compare an empire from one era with another from a different era. For example, consider the lifespan of the Roman Empire and that of the Soviet Empire. Indeed, material and military contingencies, the faster flow of people and information, and the faster and more effective spread of disinformation today make it more difficult for an empire to survive as empires of the past did. Weapons were different, customs and beliefs were different, power was centralized and passed down through families or politicians, assassinations were perceived differently from one era to another, etc.

Let's take a brief look at the Soviet Empire: it lasted for around 70 years. Not only was power centralized, but the population was also Russified through language, culture, administration, education, etc. But it takes time for one language to impose itself on another, for one culture to kill another. For example, the Baltic countries are currently composed of approximately 25-30% Russian speakers. These three countries were integrated into the USSR during World War II, but proclaimed their independence in 1990-1991. The USSR Russified the Baltic countries for fifty years by encouraging Russian population movements to these countries.

The practices used to stifle a language or culture or to make a nation disappear differ from one era to another. For example, in 17th-century Brazil, the papal power favoured the division of South America between Spain and Portugal. This is why Portugal was able to colonize Brazil, while Spain took care of the rest of South America. Colonization was also carried out in the name of God and religion, using coercive methods. The extermination of populations was also a way of transplanting another language, culture, or religion. The colonizers also used the displacement of populations to "aldeias," which were missionary villages, to change people's way of life, religion, and language, especially targeting the younger generations.

The official use of the Portuguese language in Brazilian schools was a constraint. Another way of changing the composition of a nation, which the Portuguese did, is through miscegenation. Indian women gave birth to mixed-race children, which diluted the indigenous population. Today, Brazil is a very mixed-race country. Intermarriage can therefore be encouraged or forced. Three methods were most commonly used: killing males (more or less forced intermarriage) and the forced imposition of the dominant religion. Other tactics exist, of course, such as using schools and the administration to impose a language, culture, etc.

Mixed race may not be successful: this seems to be the case in Western Europe, where the population has little mixed race with non-European populations. This reality is due to various factors, particularly when there is no policy of integration and assimilation of new arrivals, either in terms of language or culture. Religion can also act as a barrier to integration.

This can even lead to the creation of ghettos or human entities where communitarianism becomes important. It can also lead to a particular situation where entire neighbourhoods, towns, or cities are made up of a large majority of migrants who do not want to integrate culturally, for example. This means that a large number of migrants who are not integrated into the native population can lead to tensions between communities, or even ethnic tensions.

The integration of migrants must be a pedagogical art, with a proactive policy. A lack of integration can lead to conflicts and frustrations within communities. This is what the USSR sought to achieve through Russification. There have been failures, such as in the Baltic countries and Hungary, where the lingua franca is not a Slavic language but a Finno-Ugric language. However, assimilating a population and suppressing its culture and language is much easier when a people has few speakers compared to the rest of the populations surrounding the isolated people. This is particularly the case for the Uyghurs in China and the Mansi, whose autonomous territory is surrounded by a denser Russian-speaking population. In fact, only a very small minority of Mansi still speak their ancestral language, except among the elderly. In any case, the written language of the Mansi has disappeared, as schools offer Russian as a subject.

This is somewhat similar to what happened in Romania under the Ceausescu regime, where populations were displaced in order to mix the population and promote the Romanian language. Furthermore, in order to promote integration and identity unification, always tends to absorb, assimilate, and reduce minorities.

The only way to guarantee the rights of minorities is to create an autonomous region or a linguistic border, as is the case in Belgium (three linguistic regions) or Switzerland, which is composed of cantons. However, despite clear linguistic boundaries, tensions can still exist. The radical solution for eliminating a language or culture is as

follows: remove the minority language's official status, eliminate minority language schools by imposing the dominant language, displace populations to dilute the concentration of the minority, take political action to impose a single language in government offices, and establish an army, hospitals, shops, etc.

Another way of getting rid of minorities is expulsion: this was the case for the Germanic population in the former Czechoslovakia after the Second World War of 1940-1945. The population of German origin in Romania suffered the same fate after the 1940-1945 war. In a dictatorial country, sanctions may be applied for using the language of minorities; smear campaigns leading to stigmatization may exist. There may also be forms of discrimination affecting the minority population speaking a language other than that of the majority: employment, housing, etc. There was a time when speaking Hungarian was prohibited in shops, particularly in Vojvodina (now Serbia) and Romania (Satumare, Carei, Timisoara, etc.). The aim is always to reduce, assimilate, isolate, eliminate and standardize.

Ukraine's mistake was to ban the Russian language in Donbass, Crimea, and Odessa, where the majority of the population is Russian-speaking. This is one of the reasons for Russia's armed intervention in Ukraine. However, it is not only in dictatorships that a language can be banned or marginalized; this seems to be happening in the Baltic countries, where the use of Russian is not accepted because of the Russian-Ukrainian war.

Political diktats can also lead to the dismemberment of countries in order to weaken them or to circumscribe linguistic regions. This was the case in Hungary when the 1920 Treaty of Trianon led to the dismemberment of the country. Hungary lost two thirds of its territory. The population of Hungarian origin, which was still in the majority in Transylvania in 1914, gradually declined to become a minority after 1945. Currently, the proportion of the Magyar population (speaking Hungarian as their mother tongue) is less than 7% of the population.

Another issue to be discussed is the evolution of the European Union. Has the European Union abandoned the aims of its founding fathers? Has it gradually become an increasingly centralized power? Is its objective not to reduce the sovereignty of member states?

Indeed, in the aftermath of World War II, the founding fathers wanted a Europe of Six to create an economic area to increase the well-being of the populations.

With this goal of well-being in mind, an economic axis based on steel and coal enabled the Europe of Six to prosper for 30 years, with the free movement of people and goods. This was a period known as the "Trente Glorieuses" (in french) also named "Golden Sixties."

The signing of the Treaty of Rome on March 25, 1957, formally created the EEC (European Economic Community). The six-signatory countries were Belgium, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, France, Italy, and West Germany. This institution already aimed at economic, political, and social integration. However, it was not until 1968 that customs duties between the signatory countries were completely abolished.

This period of prosperity gradually came to an end with the "oil crisis" of 1974, followed by the gradual closure of coal mines, affecting Belgium and especially northern France. The loss of the Belgian Congo, which became Zaire in 1960.

European steel also began to decline gradually, due to competition and, above all, the increasing scarcity of iron ore in Belgium. As a reminder, in the 19th century, it was John Cockerill who created a steel group in Seraing. From 1981 onwards, the Cockerill-Sambre Group began to decline gradually.

In Belgium, deindustrialization was poorly managed, and Wallonia gradually became the poor part of the country, compared to Flanders, which became prosperous (and still is today). In fact, the industrial centre of gravity had shifted with the development of Sidmar in Flanders. The role of Flemish port infrastructure (Antwerp, Zeebrugge) played an important part in importing raw materials that were lacking in Belgium.

The same deindustrialization also hit France hard.

A period of turbulence ensued, particularly in Belgium, where, in the mid-1980s, the state issued high-yield treasury bills to meet its needs. The average yield on the bills reached 13%! Belgium's public debt reached 100%!

The only solution for the "common market" was enlargement in order to conquer new markets. However, enlargement undoubtedly implied the need for more complex coordination and management of affairs and the population.

With the enlargement of the "European Economic Community" in the 1990s to include the former satellite countries of the USSR (which imploded in 1991), Europe could hope for new investment and flourishing economic growth. At the end of the 1990s, euro coins and banknotes came into circulation on January 1, 2002.

In fact, on January 1, 1993, twelve countries of the European Union changed their currency.

Currently, the European Union has 27 member states. In a way, isn't this about rebuilding an empire? The European Union seems to be increasingly focused on centralizing power in the hands of a European Commission that is increasingly alienating the sovereignty of member states. As a result, those in power seem to want to create maximum centralization in order to strip member states of their power in favour of a "European

Empire” or the creation of a “United States of Europe.” This desire is part of an ideology called “globalism.” Gradually, this ideology has been rejected by some member states, such as Hungary and Slovakia, in a radical manner. However, currently, other European Union states seem to be distancing themselves from this globalism and do not wish to lose their sovereignty (Poland, Austria, Italy, etc.).

Tensions are further exacerbated by the Russian-Ukrainian war, which has gradually divided two camps: those who want peace and those in the European Commission who are determined to continue sending weapons to Ukraine to resist or defeat Russia.

The European Union has sent more than €150 billion in aid to Ukraine, hoping to destroy and fragment Russia through sanctions. The European Union is faced with a dilemma: continue a proxy war with Russia via Ukraine in the hope of weakening Russia to the point of collapse, or stop supplying weapons to Kiev and have to explain to the European people why so much money has been invested for nothing! And that's not to mention the hundreds of thousands of deaths on the front line.

The second option would put the European Union in a difficult position. How could it explain to the European populations of the member states that \$150 billion had been wasted for nothing? On the other hand, not supporting Ukraine means losing hope of integrating Ukraine into the European Union, which is in such need of raw materials and rare earths, which Ukraine possesses.

Indeed, Ukraine's integration into the European Union would undoubtedly enable European reindustrialization, leading to possible economic growth. Yes, because the European Union is in constant recession and Germany, for example, the driving force behind the European Union, is ailing. To achieve its goal, the European Union has no choice but to increasingly centralize power and create a European army, ultimately leading to a mammoth state, resembling in many ways the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics... a powerful centralized regime, with the possibility of dictatorship.

The emergence of an ideological European Union began in the 1990s, with “common values” contested by some member states. The problem is broader, insofar as the European Union, as part of the ‘West’ and its globalist ideology, is ready to impose its “values” on the world. As a reminder, the Western world represents about one billion of the eight billion people on earth.

Western countries are increasingly unpopular around the world because of their colonial past and their moralizing role. The West has shaped the world for about five centuries, but the world has changed, which the West seems not to have understood.

Currently, Asia, South America, and the Global South (Africa) seem to be increasingly questioning Western hegemony, including that of the US. This trend has begun to shape the concept of a multipolar world, as opposed to the Westerners' monopolar, globalist world. This reality means that Westerners who wanted to isolate Russia have failed and ultimately risk isolating themselves in the world.

Trust in the West has been broken, particularly because of the freezing of Russian assets (300 billion) and the interest on these assets being given to Ukraine (Russian-Ukrainian war).

This action by the West is illegal under international law and has created mistrust in the rest of the world. Under Joe Biden, the US was the spearhead of globalism and “wokism.” The current president, Donald Trump, was booed, criticized, and denigrated by European globalists during the presidential campaign. Donald Trump, who became president against all odds, despite interference, is now making the European Union pay dearly for its miscalculation: it is not Kamala Harris, but Donald Trump who has become president. The latter does not seem to have forgotten his enemies and appears to be waging a crusade against wokism and the globalist ideology of George Soros. Globalists are beginning to flee the US to take refuge in Europe, which remains the only bastion of globalists.

Is the European Union rushing down a path where ideology takes precedence over everything else, at any cost? By wanting to control everything (populations and states), is the EU not becoming a totalitarian state in the making? On what basis does the EU believe it holds the truth regarding the values it promotes? Is it democratic to want to impose its truth on the rest of the world? Does globalist ideology not engender violence that annihilates the right to have a different opinion? Is globalist ideology not monolithic, with the goal of extreme conformity in human thought, behaviour, and culture?

Doesn't the European Union weaken itself because of its ideology? Isn't its vision utopian? Why try to create a “United States of Europe” at all costs? Isn't this an attempt to recreate an empire like the Roman Empire?

The EU is very fragile because there are significant problems: poorly managed immigration, wage inequalities between member states (countries). For example, Bulgaria, where the poverty rate is very high and wages are the lowest in the Union, etc. The disparities between countries in terms of living standards are such that the “poor” wonder what the point is of being part of the EU. The populations of some countries that have abandoned their national currencies in favour of the euro are beginning to grit their teeth, as the prices of goods, services, and real estate has increased. As long as there are such disparities between regions and between Member States, cohesion remains illusory.

This existing disparity in the EU seems to have even increased in some countries, such as Bulgaria, the poorest in the EU. In Romania, a person with a full career after working as a cashier and then in a variety of roles receives a pension of around €350-400 (i.e., between €4,200 and €4,800 per year), whereas in Belgium, for example, for a full career (45 years), the minimum amount for a retirement pension at the household rate is €27,123.07 gross per year (as of February 1, 2025) according to the INASTI (National Institute for Social Insurance for Self-Employed Workers). For a single person (single rate), this minimum is €21,705.29 gross per year. In Belgium, the average statutory pension for a worker, after a full career (42 years) with an average salary, is approximately €1,663 gross per month, or approximately €22,500, including paid leave for a single person. Given that prices have been adjusted by large companies such as Aldi, Lidl, Tesco, Cora, etc., the difference between prices at Aldi or Lidl in Romania and prices in Belgium, for example, is very small. This means that a Romanian cashier with a pension of €350-400 will not have the same living conditions as a Belgian worker or self-employed person. In the many years since poor countries joined the EU, the latter has been unable to adjust salaries for the entire European population. In fact, the Romanian cashier has to live on +/- 25% of the income of a Belgian cashier. European disparity does indeed exist, which reduces the chances of social justice in the EU and undermines the possibility of social cohesion.

Another major problem for the European Union is language and culture: while the USSR was able to Russify, the EU is far from achieving this! Will it be French? German? English (even though the UK is no longer a member of the EU)? Italian? Spanish? Furthermore, what will the small Slavic countries, which together represent a large number of inhabitants, have to say?

From this point of view, the US was wiser at the time of its founding: it promptly voted for a single common language, English, even though a significant percentage of its population was of German origin.

As far as culture is concerned, the EU is rich and uniformity is impossible, as cultures have been deeply rooted for centuries. Culture has a very significant impact on populations, and destroying it is virtually impossible without pogroms or coercion. Consider what the Portuguese did, with the help of the Jesuits on the ground, to convert people to a religion, impose a single language, destroy cultures, etc.

Finally, recent events such as the Russian-Ukrainian war has forced the EU to face up to its own reflection: an "empire in the making," a behemoth with feet of clay that has gone from dependence on cheap Russian gas and oil to greater dependence on the US, with fossil fuels that cost three times as much. The EU's vassalage has been strengthened to the benefit of the US. Take, for example, the European Union's dependence on US shale gas.

Let us also not forget that the President of the European Union (who could not legally represent a member state of the European Union) met with President Donald Trump and, acting as if she were a head of state, agreed to sign a 15% tariff agreement in favour of the US, without any compensation! In addition, she signed an investment agreement worth more than \$700 billion, obliging the EU to invest for the benefit of the US. This situation has upset several European countries. The European Union's biggest mistake was to sever relations with Russia for good, thereby strengthening its vassalage to the US.

What's more, President Von der Leyen has committed the EU to purchasing approximately \$650 billion worth of US weapons. This is completely absurd: by refusing to buy very cheap Russian gas and oil, which kept its economy running, the European Union has lost any chance of developing with Russia, which was only too willing to cooperate economically. Of course, the US is rubbing its hands with glee: no more Europe-Russia economic axis, and on top of that, the EU has increased its dependence on the US. As the EU is experiencing increasing internal tensions, isn't it rushing headlong into trouble by always talking about war rather than working to improve the well-being of the Union's populations?

The European Union has become belligerent, breaking with the aspirations of its founding fathers: to strive for the well-being of its people. In this respect, we are far from the mark! A major recession began in 2022 and continues to worsen with the severing of relations with Russia, the loss of confidence in the Global South, and the fact that the EU is considering sanctioning China to follow the orders of its suzerain. Has the EU not shot itself in the foot? Is it not at risk of isolating itself and becoming totally dependent on the US? When will we see a mature Europe taking control of its own destiny and seeking economic alliances rather than being obsessed with war? Won't what remains of Ukraine, a largely corrupt and war-torn country, be an impossible burden to bear? One hypothesis is that the West, having failed to bring Russia to its knees in over three years, is considering provoking a war of attrition in the hope of weakening Russia. But what could happen if Russia used tactical nuclear bombs in case Russia felt it was losing? Not to mention the possible military alliances against the West. Isn't this war nonsense?

Isn't it ultimately in the US's interest to control a weakened Europe?

Bad EU policy? Ideological blindness? The impoverishment of the EU population is likely to worsen with the significant increase in the cost of living since 2022. The poor have become poorer and increasingly marginalized, and the middle class has shrunk, particularly due to energy prices and the cost of food: many housewives can no longer make ends meet.

III. The USSR, an empire dying and losing its satellite countries

The implosion of the USSR was the collapse of an empire that can be traced back to 1991, although the warning signs were already there long before that. In Hungary, for example, where the standard of living was one of the highest in the Eastern Bloc, the economy began to deteriorate in the early 1980s, with the liberation of the satellite countries in 1989.

The collapse of the planning system was brutal due to corruption, low productivity, a decline in consumer goods, and national debt.

The arms race and wars (especially in Afghanistan) took their toll on the economy. Finally, a large part of the population no longer believed in Marxist-Leninist ideology and dreamed of living in the Western lifestyle. Despite President Gorbachev's efforts to open up the market and increase freedom of expression (1985-1991) with "Perestroika" (meaning restructuring) and Glasnost (meaning transparency), his efforts came too late.

Nationalist movements began to appear in 1988 (in the Baltic states) and even in Russia, where nationalists claimed the primacy of "Great and Holy Russia" over Soviet law. An attempted coup against Gorbachev on August 19, 1991, failed thanks to Boris Yeltsin. However, this coup left its mark, and the official dissolution of the USSR took place on December 25, 1991. This official dissolution took place in Minsk, Belarus, where three signatories were present: Russia, Belarus, and Ukraine. Thus, the USSR broke up and 15 republics became independent countries.

This breakup caused great instability in the republics, as well as conflicts. For example, Moldova was a republic with a Russian minority in the north and south. In the north, Transnistria declared itself a republic that only Russia would recognize. Currently, it is the only "country" where the population continues to live according to Soviet ideology.

Other conflicts took place, for example in Ossetia, Chechnya, etc. But on a more positive note, a new structure emerged with the creation of the "Commonwealth of Independent States" (CIS). The CIS made it possible to maintain special ties between the former republics.

What about the other states? The Baltic countries became independent and hastened to join NATO and the EU, much to Russia's displeasure. Why? Because the West had promised Russia that it would not expand NATO to its borders in exchange for accepting the reunification of the two Germanys. The deal was not respected, and for Russia, touching Ukraine (a buffer zone between NATO and Russia) was the last straw. This is another major reason for the Russian-Ukrainian conflict, which is in reality a disguised war between NATO and Russia, fought through a proxy war.

IV. Reflections on the fall of the USSR, the Russian-Ukrainian war, and globalization

The collapse of the USSR was a godsend for the West. Indeed, this collapse meant that the US became the world's only military power, the master of the world. The idea of globalization gained ground in the early 1990s. The idea of imposing Western culture, Western hegemony, Western values, and why not the dream of the dislocation of Russia, the world's largest country with vast untapped resources and a population of only about 145 million.

The idea of the globalization of power was supported by the liberal left, and the proxy war with Russia was amplified by the Biden administration, which sent billions in weapons to Ukraine. Some politicians followed suit by dissuading Ukraine from signing a peace agreement with Russia.

Putin became president and, in record time, turned around Russia's economy and modernized its army. The Russian-Ukrainian war began on February 24, 2022, with Russia's invasion of Ukraine. A first attempt to sign a peace agreement failed in March-April 2022, first in Belarus and then in Istanbul. Russia accused the West of manoeuvring to prevent peace from being achieved and specifically accused France and Germany of deceiving it and of actually wanting to buy time for Ukraine to rearm. Everything suggests that the Russian-Ukrainian war actually began in 2014 and not in February 2022 when Russia began to invade Ukraine.

President Putin took Crimea without firing a single shot and began his "special intervention" (invasion on February 24, 2022) to come to the aid of Russian speakers who had been oppressed by the Kiev regime since 2014. Kiev was bombing the Luhansk and Donetsk Oblasts. These two Oblasts represent the Donbass region, rich in minerals and rare earths. In Odessa, Ukrainian forces committed murders of Russian speakers, which exasperated Russia. The situation escalated when Russia recognized the two Oblasts (February 21, 2022). Russia then annexed the Oblasts of Zaporizhia and Kherson.

After a counterattack by Kiev forces hoping to defeat Russia with logistical and weapons support from NATO forces, Russia adapted and strengthened its war machine. Since the war began, Russia has also been able to adapt to sanctions imposed by Western countries, despite the prediction of a French minister who, at the time, promised to bring the Russian economy to its knees. Although Russia initially appeared to be isolated, it has managed to circumvent the sanctions and, above all, find other economic partners. The ban on using the SWIFT system has also been skilfully circumvented, and since the end of 2024, Russia seems to have been able to overcome the difficulties caused by the sanctions.

Contrary to Western hopes, the 18 packages of sanctions (soon to be 19?), the freezing of Russian assets, and the redistribution of interest (without legal basis) to finance Ukraine seem to have “cooled” some countries' confidence in the West. Africa is one example, where France has lost a lot of economic interest. Hasn't this breach of trust been reinforced by the hypocrisy of applying “double standards” and the fact that the West has arrogated to itself the right to do what it forbids other nations to do?

All this has destabilized the world order, creating a new geopolitical situation. The BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa), created in 2009, have opened the door to other countries: Iran, Egypt, the United Arab Emirates, Indonesia, and Ethiopia. Other countries seeking to escape Western influence will undoubtedly want to join. The BRICS countries are likely to become a serious rival to the Group of Seven (G7) rich countries. It is clear that the West risks being marginalized. The US does not welcome the economic expansion of the BRICS countries, especially if they plan to use a currency other than the US dollar for transactions.

The Russian-Ukrainian war has created the conditions for a rapprochement between China and Russia, but also a rapprochement with India, which has not forgotten that it was a British colony.

The Russian-Ukrainian war has not isolated Russia at all (as the West had hoped). South Africa has come to Russia's defence, as have certain other powerful countries such as Brazil. African countries have increased trade with China and Russia. Africa is turning its back on the West because, in its view, of the West's neocolonial behaviour and its “double standards.” If the West, representing nearly one billion people, does not change its way of thinking and acting, it is the West that risks being isolated from the rest of the world, representing seven billion people. Doesn't the United States have an interest in Europe becoming bogged down in this war alone, while enriching itself by selling arms to the European Union? And at the same time, tightening its grip on Europe? The United States has every interest in ensuring that Europe does not form an economic powerhouse with Russia.

V. The sabotage of the Nord Stream gas pipelines: who benefits from the crime?

The US has never looked favourably on the possibility of Germany strengthening its economic ties with Russia. Indeed, such an alliance (between Europe and Russia) would represent a danger to the US both economically and politically.

The sabotage of Nord Stream under the Baltic Sea was intentional, aimed at radically cutting off the flow of gas to Germany.

To date, the Italian authorities have arrested a Ukrainian suspect who has finally admitted to participating in the sabotage. It should be noted that the mainstream media had accused Russia of sabotaging the pipelines! Germany had not shown much motivation to find the culprits, even though it had invested billions in the construction.

Following this sabotage, Germany, Europe's leading economy, had to turn to shale gas from the US, which is highly polluting and about three times more expensive than Russian gas. This situation has been catastrophic for German industry, with companies going bankrupt and relocating, particularly to the US and elsewhere. The breakdown of Europe's engine had a significant impact on the cost of living for the European population. The dream of integrating Ukraine into the EU could have revitalized Europe by providing it with what it lacks to be independent from both Russia and the US.

But one thing the EU did not foresee was the purchase of Ukraine's rich black soil for wheat production by US economic powers. President Trump has signed an agreement with the Ukrainian president for concessions to exploit minerals and rare earths. What will remain for the EU? Will it not be the fall guy?

Europe is becoming poorer and can no longer provide for its population, businesses continue to close their doors or relocate to the US or elsewhere, and an economic collapse is looming. Is this the US's goal? It would be foolish to lose a loyal ally that is completely under its control. However, social unrest is likely to occur, as the EU is in poor economic health. Isn't the EU at risk of imploding due to discontent among the poorer member states of Central and Eastern Europe? As the saying goes, “He who grasps at too much loses everything!” Hasn't the EU's appetite been too big, with 27 member states that it seems to have difficulty managing? Moreover, we are seeing growing dissatisfaction among the populations of certain countries and governments.

Europe has become a giant in terms of services rendered and finished products, without having any raw materials. It made a monumental mistake when it did everything it could to reject Turkey, a country of more than a million square kilometres with resources, not to mention its interesting geopolitical position (access to the Silk Road, access between the Black Sea and the Mediterranean, its labour pool, etc.).

VI. An alternative world: a globalist vision or a multipolar world and the development of the BRICS

The fratricidal war (between Ukrainians and Russians) and the march of globalization have undoubtedly boosted the development of the BRICS, which has become an economic giant in terms of population and GDP,

rivaling other entities such as the European Union and the economic sphere of the Anglo-Saxon countries. This globalization was originally planned by the Anglo-Saxon world. Similarly, wokism, which originated in the Anglo-Saxon world, gradually spread, becoming a cultural norm, and even a value to be imposed on the rest of the world.

Globalism aims to subject the world to a political, economic, social, and cultural force over the countries of the world. This could result in a world government subjugating nations. Globalism is a utopia; however, if it were to become a reality, it could lead to A. Huxley's "Brave New World."

The BRICS countries are therefore becoming an alternative to the globalist movement, a counter-force, whose goals include the preservation of free trade between nations that respect each other: business without cultural, social, or value constraints to be accepted by others. Sovereignty is a reality that is gaining strength and making itself heard, whether in countries resisting globalism within the European Economic Community (the EU) or around the world.

Are the values promoted by Westerners universal? Certainly not! For example, there was a time when pederasty was a common value in Ancient Greece, the Roman Empire, feudal Japan, among the Celts, etc. The master-slave status in the Roman Empire seemed to be a normal thing, and the massacre of Indians in South and North America seemed to serve no purpose for a long time.

During the Renaissance, pederasty also existed. Were nations and warlords not prepared to commit pogroms in order to appropriate territory or wipe out a population? This was also the case with the Aborigines of Australia, and segregation of Black people in the US still existed in the 1960s.

"*The Genocide of the Americas* shows how 90% to 95% of the original population of the American continent was eliminated by European colonists."

(Grondin, Marcel & Viezzer Moema, *The Genocide of the Americas, Resistance and Survival of Indigenous Populations, Ecosociété*).

It is clear that the values promoted are therefore ephemeral in nature; values that are encouraged or demanded in a country, a community, a civilization. The civilizational problem arises when one civilization wants to force other civilizations to adopt its values, either through politics or coercion (a coup to put someone who shares the same values at the head of the state, economic constraints and sanctions, coercion, the uprising of minorities sponsored by the authorities or NGOs to exert influence, etc.).

When the values of one civilization become a constraint on another civilization, tensions, conflicts, political influences, economic sanctions, and wars can arise. The dominant party almost always uses double standards, leading to "two weights, two measures": what I can do, you cannot! Does the end justify the means? Nowadays, countries can exert pressure, apply sanctions, create riots to overthrow a power that is causing trouble, etc.

VII. The awakening of identity and the demands of the Global South in the face of the West's "double standards"

It is often said that "Americans have no friends, only interests" (Charles de Gaulle). Henry John Temple said the following in the House of Commons in 1848: "We have no eternal allies, and we have no perpetual enemies. Our interests are eternal and perpetual, and those interests it is our duty to follow."

Are interests more important than human beings? Does the end justify the means? Although the US, the world's leading military power, has provoked numerous wars, overthrown regimes, and fomented revolts, it has rarely won a war. There have even been debacles such as in Afghanistan, wars declared for fallacious reasons, such as in Iraq under President George W. Bush, a war that ended with around one million deaths due to sanctions that deprived the population of medicine and water. It is surprising, moreover, that those responsible have not been tried by the International Court of Justice. Reasons of state are often opaque and superior.

We have already seen UN positions being flouted or disregarded, or states intervening in other states without UN approval; worse still, the armed intervention of NATO, which should be an organization of peace and protection.

NATO's involvement in the war in Yugoslavia without a mandate is one example. Other examples of intervention are terrible, such as the wars in Iraq, Libya, etc. Very often, conflicts are prepared by political intrigues and economic interests or the desire to gain control of a country's natural resources. The dream of Victor Hugo or Mazzini and Garibaldi to create a United States of Europe contradicts the sovereignty of states. The United States of Europe would be led by a handful of tribunes from the most powerful countries in Europe, dictating the laws to the detriment of smaller countries.

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